

Dynamic modeling of a two stage spur gear system

ELYOUSFI BILAL¹, SOUALHI ABDNOUR², MEDJAHER KAMAL³, GUILLET FRANÇOIS⁴, ELBADAOUI MOHAMED⁵
^{1,2,4,5}Laboratoire Analyse des Signaux & des Processus Industriels, Université Jean Monnet de Saint Etienne
³Laboratoire génie de production, Ecole Nationale d'Ingénieurs de Tarbes
 Email : bilal.elyousfi@univ-st-etienne.fr

Abstract

Nowadays, geared systems are widely used in industrial applications such as automobiles, wind turbines, airplanes and other rotary machines. Gears generally undergo high service load, harsh operating conditions and inevitable fatigue [1]; this is why maintainers consider them as a critical component. Therefore, early fault detection and diagnosis of gears leads to operational and maintenance cost reductions and ensure people safety; spur gear dynamic model can help to understand faults generation mechanism and to develop an effective faults detection and diagnosis methods. Models proposed in the literature can be gathered into three categories according to the method used for time varying mesh stiffness (TVMS) evaluation: analytical methods [2], finite element methods [3] and experimental methods [4]. Another classification of these models can be done following the number of parameters considered in the study like shafts torsional deformation and bearings stiffness and damping. In this study, the potential energy method proposed by Yang and Lin [5], is used to compute the TVMS of the gear pairs considering the hertzian component, bending component, shear component, axial compressive component and torsional component of the gear body, a 10 DOF model is developed to describe the dynamic behavior of a two stage gearbox including the bearing and the shafts stiffness. MATLAB Ode solvers are used for the resolution of the differential equation system to estimate the different quantities such as vibration and velocity in both healthy and faulty conditions.

Key word: gear modeling, potential energy method, diagnostics, time varying mesh stiffness.

Results

Figure 1a, 1b, 1c, 1d represent the TVMS evolution despite the first shaft angle, 1a represents the healthy gear stiffness, 1b represents the deformation of the meshing stiffness with different crack sizes, 1c represents the deformation resulting of a spall in the tooth tip and 1d represent the case of a broken tooth. The dashed line refers to the healthy TVMS in each case.

Figure 1: Stiffness vs. angular displacement θ_1 of perfect gears (a); cracked gears (b); spalled gears (c) and gears with broken tooth (d).

Table 1 specifies the different parameters used for the simulation of the dynamic model.

Material	Steel: $E = 2.068 \times 10^{11} \text{ Pa}$; $\nu = 0.3$
Modulus	$m_1 = m_2 = 2$
Teeth numbers	$Z_1 = 19$ et $Z_2 = 25$, $Z_3 = 19$ et $Z_4 = 25$
Pressure angle	$\alpha = 20^\circ$
Input frequency	$F_1 = 25 \text{ Hz}$

Table 1: simulation parameters

Figure 2a, 2b, 2c, 2d represent respectively the linear acceleration of the first pinion in healthy conditions, cracked gear, spalled gear and a gear with a broken tooth. One can detect the two meshing periods $T_1 = 0.0021\text{s}$ of the first stage and $T_2 = 0.0028\text{s}$ of the second stage; a crack or a spall cause a local amplification of the vibration at the fault position, the case of a broken tooth is drawn in two revolutions to show the high level of vibration it causes.

Figure 2: vibration y_1 of perfect gears (a); cracked gears (b); spalled gears (c) and gears with broken tooth (d).

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